
Sociological Study of the PVTGs Tribal Communities in India and the Path to Sustainable Development: A Case Study of the Kolam Tribe

Dr. Seema Vithalrao Shete

Assistant Professor of Sociology, Savitri Jotirao Social Work College, Yavatmal

Corresponding Author – Dr. Seema Vithalrao Shete

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Introduction:

In Indian society, tribal communities are relatively more distant from development compared to rural and urban communities. The key reasons for this are their residence in remote areas, isolation, self-centered lifestyle, resistance to change, social, economic, and educational backwardness, and lack of basic infrastructure. Among the various tribal communities in the country, 75 tribes are categorized as Particularly Vulnerable Tribal Groups (P.V.T.G.), which are considered to be in urgent need of protection. In Maharashtra, the Kolam, Katkari, and Madiya tribes are recognized as P.V.T.G.s. These tribes are far removed from

development and are severely disadvantaged in terms of social, economic, and educational progress.

For the sustainable development of these backward and preservable tribal groups, a multi-dimensional sociological study of their life systems is essential. This study will help identify the root causes of their problems, analyze the reasons behind their backwardness, and highlight the gaps in the welfare and developmental efforts made by the government. A sociological research study of the Kolam tribe, for example, could be highly beneficial in bringing them into the mainstream of development.

Keywords: *Tribal Communities, Most-Backward Tribes, P.V.T.G., Kolam Tribe, Kolam Pod, Customs, Traditions, Sociology, Sociological Study, Sustainable Development, Progress, Socio-Economic-Educational Status, Livelihood, Religious Practices, Superstition, Forest Produce, Firewood Collection, School Dropouts, Single Parenting, Tuberculosis, Anemia, etc.*

Objectives:

1. To provide a overview of the Kolam tribe.
2. To identify the issues faced by the Kolam tribe.
3. To analyze the causes of the problems faced by the Kolam tribe from a sociological perspective.
4. To provide recommendations or suggestions for the sustainable development of the Kolam tribe based on the conclusions drawn from the sociological study, and to propose a pathway for their sustainable development along with practical strategies for implementation.

Research Methodology:

For this study, primary data collection was carried out using interviews as the key technique. The study area was identified as *Chhaparda Kolam Pod*. Interviews were conducted with various stakeholders such as the ASHA (Accredited Social Health Activist) worker, social workers, president of the Forest Rights Management Committee, school dropouts, young mothers, etc. to collect data. Additionally, secondary sources such as research papers, theses, and books were consulted to support and enhance the study.

Analysis & Interpretation of Facts:**A Overview of the Kolam Tribe:**

The Kolam tribe is an indigenous group primarily found in the Yavatmal district, with a presence in Nanded, Adilabad, Wardha, and Chandrapur districts as well. According to the 2011 Census, the population of the Kolam tribe stands at 1,94,671 (one lakh, ninety-four thousand, six hundred seventy-one).

The Kolam people primarily work as agricultural laborers. In addition, they sustain themselves through activities like farming, collecting forest produce, hunting, and daily wage labor. The tribe faces significant educational attrition and shows a high degree of educational backwardness. Consequently, the proportion of Kolam individuals in employment is very low. Due to extreme poverty in most families, establishing small-scale, cottage, or large businesses becomes practically impossible. As a result, they are forced to rely on a limited economic life or status.

The Kolam tribe lacks formal political organization or influential

leadership. As a result, their representation in key political positions such as Members of Parliament, Members of Legislative Assembly, or Ministers is virtually non-existent. For example, in the Ralegaon constituency, the Kolam tribe has a significant number of tribal voters, yet they do not have any political leadership. This reflects a part of their political apathy and awareness.

However, within the Kolam community, there exists an internal political structure in the form of a "*Panchamandal*" (a male-centered organizational leadership), which is relatively influential.

Religious and Cultural Life:

The religious and cultural life of the Kolam people is distinctive. They are deeply influenced by religion and tradition. They regularly worship their village deities and family deities, such as *Bhimayyak*, *Muddal Kon*, and *Mahurta Devi*. Following traditional religious practices is an integral part of their lives. They celebrate many festivals, such as *Gaobandhani*, *Mohdombari*, and *Moharram*, with great enthusiasm and collective participation, which is a unique feature of their culture.

However, superstition also plays a significant role in their lives. For instance, they strictly observe certain customs, such as the prohibition of women during their menstrual cycle for five days and the ritual associated with childbirth, which involves a specific 38-day purification period. They tend to associate any illness with being afflicted by spirits or evil forces. In such cases, rituals such as placing an egg or a chicken on the afflicted person's body are performed, as they believe that the illness or bad luck is transferred to the egg or chicken.

These beliefs and practices are prevalent in many aspects of Kolam life.

Family Life:

Like other tribal communities, the Kolam tribe also exhibits the characteristic of the "unstable family." It is common for individuals to decide to separate for various reasons or to leave their partners, which is referred to as "*kadi-mod*" (a term for separation). The death of a partner is also a frequent occurrence within these families. The disruptive nature of such family breakdowns has a significant negative impact on the upbringing, education, and overall personality development of children. As a result, children often become disconnected from the educational process. This issue is notably evident in the community.

Health Issues:

The government, through programs like the ASHA workers, *Anganwadi* workers, and the healthcare system, is trying to ensure the preservation of life among the Kolam people. However, health issues such as anemia, malnutrition, tuberculosis, and general weakness are prevalent within the community.

Identifying the Issues of the Kolam Tribe:

To examine the issues faced by the Kolam tribe, a study was conducted in the context of the *Chhaparda Kolam Pod* in the Kalam Taluka. This pod is located at a distance of about one to one and a half kilometers from the *Chhaparda* village, situated on the mountain's peak and foothills. The pod consists of 35 families with a total population of 159, including 73 men and 86 women. Among them, there are

13 adolescent girls and 12 children enrolled in the *Anganwadi*.

Out of the 35 families, only 11 families (31%) have agricultural land. The remaining families rely on daily wage labor and forest-based livelihoods. Approximately 80% of the families own chickens and goats, but these do not generate significant income. The number of families owning cows, buffaloes, or oxen is extremely low. Since the Kolam community does not have sustainable means of livelihood, there is a lack of certainty regarding their income. Additionally, there is a shortage of regular employment opportunities, leading to the problem of seasonal unemployment. As a result, many people migrate to the Kalam and Yavatmal regions to work as construction laborers or brick kiln workers. Hunting and collecting forest produce supplement their livelihoods, but these activities do not yield consistent or reliable income.

Economic Life:

In the *Chhaparda Kolam Pod*, people collect *tendu* leaves during the summer season and are forced to sell them to contractors at very low rates. This provides them with some financial income. However, there is a lack of bamboo cultivation or production in the area, so they do not engage in making or selling bamboo products. The local people primarily use *Moha* Flower for personal purposes, but they are unable to make and sell food items from it. This is due to the scarcity of abundant resources and the lack of an entrepreneurial perspective.

In addition, they collect other forest products like *tendu*, *charoli*, and *gum (dink)* whenever available and sell them in the

weekly markets. However, this does not generate significant income.

In the community, issues related to the health of migrant workers, women's safety, and children's education often arise. These problems are likely to be experienced by Kolam migrant workers. Young people are burdened with family responsibilities at a young age, forcing them into labor, construction work, or employment as seasonal workers. This results in a rise in migration, addiction, and a lack of access to education and health services among the youth.

Addiction:

In the pod, some individuals exhibit unhealthy habits such as drinking alcohol, smoking, using tobacco, and chewing betel leaves. The number of people who drop out of education in the pod is higher than the number of those who continue their studies. The number of graduates is low, and those employed in regular jobs are very few. (Shete, 2018, page -254)

Marriage:

In the pod, a girl is considered ready for marriage once she reaches marriageable age, and a boy is seen as suitable for marriage when he becomes a breadwinner or engages in labor. The legal age for marriage is often overlooked in these practices. However, some educated and aware individuals intervene to prevent child marriage.

Educational Dropout:

When examining the reasons behind children dropping out of school or college, one major factor observed is that the child's parents are either separated, the mother is a single parent, or one or both parents are deceased. In such cases, the child is often

cared for by the grandmother. Elderly grandmothers, especially those without support, face the challenge of raising grandchildren, making it difficult for them to prioritize the children's education. For these children, survival and daily sustenance often take precedence over education.

In many instances, even when children wish to continue their studies, the caregivers (often grandparents) are unable to provide the necessary support for their education.

Often, even when children wish to pursue education, those who care for them, either out of helplessness or compulsion, discourage them by saying, "Don't study, go work." Such statements demotivate the children and prevent them from feeling encouraged to pursue education or even from arguing for it. This clearly establishes a direct link between unstable family structures and interruptions in children's education.

Furthermore, in many Kolam families, there is a sense of inferiority or indifference towards education. For example, phrases like "What will education do? Will it get us a job?" or "What use is education for us? Better focus on farming or manual labor" are commonly heard within families. This attitude leads children to distance themselves from education.

When asked why they dropped out of school, children often respond simply with, "They (the family) don't learn,. So, how can I?"

In essence, the Kolam community, which is not very aware of formal education, often finds itself drifting away from educational pursuits due to the daily struggles of survival.

Health:

In discussions with ASHA workers, it was revealed that there are 4 TB patients in the pod. Due to the strong influence of religion and superstition, combined with economic hardships, illnesses are often attributed to spiritual causes. People resort to various superstitious treatments such as tying threads, using lime and chilies, applying eggs or chickens, or seeking help from traditional healers (*bhagat*). As a result, these practices sometimes lead to death.

There is a need for greater awareness about these issues. The ASHA workers in the area are proactive and sensitive, and they coordinate well on health-related matters.

Although the government provides health facilities, many Kolam families still prefer to conduct childbirth at home. This mindset is common in the community. Superstitions related to menstruation and childbirth is strictly followed. For example, in the Singledip Kolam Pod in Yavatmal district, girls still bathe in the open during their menstrual periods and live separately, resembling the "*kormaghar*" (seclusion) practice seen in the Madia tribe in Gadchiroli district.

It is evident that the Kolam community is heavily influenced by traditions and customs. Additionally, the community often exhibits an inward-looking, self-centered lifestyle, leading to a situation where their way of life remains steeped in outdated practices that create social and personal challenges.

Lack of Political Organization and Effective Leadership among the Kolams

The above issues and their underlying causes were highlighted through a study conducted in the Chhaparda Kolam Pod, which serves as a representative area.

The Kolam community often faces challenges in accessing government schemes or higher education due to the lack of proof of citizenship. Additionally, frequent changes in tribal policies make it difficult to achieve sustainable development goals for the community. These are some of the concerns that have been raised.

Conclusion:

To resolve the issues faced by the Kolam community, the following remedial measures should be taken:

- **Raising Awareness About Education:** It is essential to raise awareness about the importance of education among Kolam families and children. Various mediums such as street plays, guidance programs, and public awareness campaigns should be used to emphasize the significance of education. It is equally important to motivate them through educational encouragement.
- **Addressing Dropout Rates:** A detailed study of the school and college dropout rates among Kolam children should be conducted, and action plans with remedial measures should be implemented to address these issues.
- **Education as a Tool for Change:** Education is an effective tool for transformation. The development of the Kolam community can be accelerated through educational empowerment. Focus should be on

achieving this goal through education.

- **Creating Sustainable Livelihoods:** The Kolam community should be provided with sustainable means of livelihood. They should be made beneficiaries of the Forest Rights Act. Forest Rights Management Committees need to be made active, and forest-based livelihoods should be promoted. It is crucial to mobilize tribal resources based on their local area.
- **Health Preservation and Promotion:** The health preservation and promotion of the Kolam community should be carried out following the approach and methodology of the 'SEARCH' organization, founded by PadmaShri Dr. Abhay & Ranitai Bang in Gadchiroli district. This model should be adopted for the health management of the Kolam community, ensuring systematic execution and organizational implementation.
- **Eradicating Superstitions and Harmful Traditions:** To eliminate the detrimental impact of traditional religious customs, rituals, and superstitions among the Kolams, a campaign against superstitions should be launched. During this process, it is important to respect their culture and beliefs, win their trust, and highlight the dangers of superstitions, thereby bringing about social change.
- **Preventing Family Breakdown:** Efforts should be made to prevent

family breakdowns or separations within Kolam families. Counseling services should be provided to couples to ensure family unity.

- **Women's Safety and Health Needs:** The need for comfort and support for women, particularly during menstruation and childbirth, should be emphasized. Focus should be on ensuring the safety and secure environment for women.
- **Improved Health Services:** Health services for the Kolam communities should be made more accessible, with increased responsiveness from health systems. The provision of mobile doctors and healthcare facilities should be made available.
- **Provision of Citizenship Proofs:** The government should take effective steps to provide citizenship proofs for every individual in the Kolam families to ensure they can access government schemes and other services.
- **NGO Support and Volunteer Leadership:** NGOs should be involved in this process. Additionally, volunteers and leaders should be developed within each pod so that they can independently manage the documentation processes and overcome challenges, helping each pod become self-sufficient.
- **Identifying Needs Through Community Bodies:** The exact needs of the Kolam community will emerge through forums such as the *GramSabha*, *Mahila Sabha*, and *Yuvati Sabha*. Based on these needs, solutions will be suggested through

public participation, and their voluntary involvement in implementing these solutions can be effectively encouraged. Therefore, organizational development of the Kolam community is crucial. Increasing their initiative and participation in the development and decision-making processes can significantly contribute to their overall progress.

- **Involvement in Local Governance:** It is important to include Kolam representatives in local governance to ensure their active participation in community development.
- **Increasing Participation in Decision-Making:** Actively increasing the Kolam community's participation and leadership in the decision-making and development processes is essential.
- **Preserving and Promoting Cultural Heritage:** The cultural heritage of the Kolam community should be preserved and promoted as **national folk art**, reaching a global audience.
- **Primary Education and Literature in Kolam Language:** Providing primary education in the Kolam language and creating literature in the language should be prioritized for preserving their cultural identity.

Summary:

This study discusses the Kolam tribe (a PVTG), examining their way of life, addressing their issues, and identifying root causes. To achieve their holistic development, it is crucial to conduct a

detailed analysis, strategic planning, and effective interventions for each aspect of their lives. Building organization and leadership within the community is essential. Only then can the Kolams be integrated into the mainstream development process. Similar studies should be conducted for all 75 PVTG tribes, with a special focus on their development. Sociological research is vital for this purpose.

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